

Development and evaluation of training module on ergonomics in dentistry for undergraduate dental students- A cross sectional study

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Abstract:

Background: Maintaining correct body posture during long hours for dental practice is the key for avoiding musculoskeletal disorders. It is important to impress the principles of ergonomics upon the students right from their formative years.

Aim: This study was a cross-sectional study to assess the efficacy of a training module regarding dental implications of principles of ergonomics using pre and post design

Results: The overall response rate was 64% (138 out of 200). There was significant improvement in the knowledge as well as practices regarding body posture while working, evident from the test scores

Conclusion: This module can be considered for curriculum enrichment in undergraduate training.

Introduction:

Ergonomics can be defined as an applied science concerned with designing and arranging things people use so that the people and things interact most efficiently and safely. The term work related musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) refers to musculoskeletal disorders that are made worse or longer lasting by work conditions or workplace risk factors. Common examples of such workplace risk factors include jobs requiring repetitive, forceful or prolonged exertions of the hands; pushing or pulling, or carrying of heavy objects and prolonged awkward postures^{1,2}.

The nature of the dental profession and the postures assumed by the dentist has a huge impact on the dentist's body and carries with it a high risk of musculoskeletal disorders. Musculoskeletal disorders can affect the body's muscle, joints, tendon, ligaments and nerves. Sound knowledge regarding ergonomics is a basic requirement for facilitating the balanced musculoskeletal health that will enable longer, healthier career, enhance productivity and minimize MSDs among dentist. With a little attention dentist can improve their comfort on the job during the course of their career^{3,4}. Therefore, this study is designed to evaluate the knowledge, attitude and perception of dental students concerning ergonomics and work-related musculoskeletal disorders with the help of training module.

Aim:

To evaluate the effect of a training module regarding ergonomics & musculoskeletal disorders in dental students.

Objectives:

- 1) To develop training module regarding musculoskeletal disorders.
- 2) Assess its effectiveness in dental students using pre and post questionnaire

Materials and Methods:

Study design:

Analytical cross-sectional study with pre and post design.

Sample size:

A total of 200 dental students (III & IV year BDS) were included in the study.

Methodology:

A questionnaire containing 15 questions pertaining to the knowledge, attitude and perception towards musculoskeletal disorders was used in the study. A specific module was developed to train the students regarding importance of correct body posture and various musculoskeletal disorders. Later same questionnaire was used to evaluate the change in knowledge, attitude and perception of students toward MSDs and conclusions were drawn based on the response of the participants.

Module:

Contents:

- 1) What is Ergonomics and its application in dentistry
- 2) General mistakes done by dentists while working
- 3) What are Musculoskeletal disorders?

Definition, Signs, Symptoms and treatment

- 4) Tips to avoid musculoskeletal disorders by improving working posture

The training module was conducted by qualified prosthodontist. It consisted of didactic session detailing all principles of good and bad body postures. It was followed by demonstration on how to maintain appropriate body posture during working in dental clinic. Several images, scientific articles and videos were also shared for their reference.

Results:

Response rate was 64%. Out of the 138 dental students participating in the study, 101 were females and 37 were males. Table 1 summarizes the overall improvement in the responses from the participants in percentages.

Chi-squared test revealed no significant differences between different genders or years of study ($P=0.134$). The mean (SD) values of knowledge before and after the education were estimated at 6.9 ± 3.4 and 12.5 ± 2.7 , respectively. Paired-sample t-test revealed a significant difference between the knowledge scores before and after the intervention ($P=0.00$).

Discussion

According to ISO 11226 standards, the optimal neutral posture is one in which the musculoskeletal system is not overworked and maximal control and strength are still possible.

The dentist should work in a seated posture with a minimum angle of 110 degrees between the dentist's thighs and abdomen, as suggested by European Society of Dental Ergonomics (ESDE). It also

suggests that the two legs of the dentist should lie beneath the backrest of the patient dental chair. This will provide dentists greater approximation and range of motion to accommodate their sight and approach requirements in the intraoral work field. Consequently, the dentist has more flexibility to take on a more dynamic posture and to move their body more freely around the chair, as per ESDE^{5,6}.

As a result, there is less need for extreme bending of the upper limbs, which makes it easier to assume a neutral working posture and results in less overloading of the muscles and skeleton. For instance, the mesial, distal, buccal, and lingual/palatal tooth surfaces are directed in opposite directions, and the dentist must see them when doing dental scaling operations. The dentist will naturally lean excessively and assume an unnatural posture if there is no room for the dentist to reposition their body so that the patient's dental surface is in front of their eyes.

When treating patients, dentists frequently place a high value on visualization and frequently overlook the neutral posture that is required during treatment.

Although importance of correct body posture cannot be overemphasized for dental professionals, there is still a widespread prevalence of musculoskeletal disorders among this population.

It is a common observation that despite being aware of the proper sitting posture, the students regularly adopt incorrect postures in an attempt to enhance their visualization while working.

Therefore, at the time of their formative years during their graduation, students should receive a positive reinforcement regarding practicing correct body posture as it goes long way in maintaining healthy skeletal system.

Regardless of gender or year of study, ergonomics training module was found to be beneficial in improving dental students' knowledge, attitudes, and practices. Thus, specific training has been shown to improve the psychosocial and biomechanical components linked to issues with occupational health. Stetler et al. have highlighted that the problem of MSDs may be successfully solved by using multi-interventional approaches, such as removing risk factors in addition to educational initiatives.

Such module should be included in the clinical training curriculum and students should also be assessed on this parameter to foster ergonomically correct working position.

Conclusion:

Specific training module for ergonomics in dentistry was overall effective for the current population in improving their knowledge, attitude and practices regarding correct working body posture.

References:

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Table 1: Responses from the participants in percentages

S N	Question	Pre test	Post test
1	Are you aware of work-related musculoskeletal disorders?	66%- No 11% Not sure	100% Yes
2	Are you aware of the term 'Ergonomics' and its implications in dentistry?	87%- No 9%- not sure	100% Yes
3	If yes, then are you following principles of Ergonomics in your practice?	89% No 7% Not sure	93% Yes
4	Dentist Should work in neutral position. (Neutral position- Maintain 'S Curve' of the spine)	56% Yes 27% Not sure	99% Yes
5	Prolonged static position can lead to back, neck or shoulder pain or musculoskeletal disorders.	79% Yes	100% Yes
6	Ergonomic principles apply only to dentist position, but not to equipment's	48%- Yes 39% not sure	100% Both
7	Dentist Should use ergonomically designed instruments (Light weight, large handle diameter, texturing on handle for proper grip)	47%- Yes 37% not sure	100% Yes
8	Use of excessive forces during clinical work by dentist can lead to musculoskeletal disorders.	43% Yes 37% not sure	100% Yes
9	Sharp instruments are essential for reducing excessive forces during instrumentation.	89% Yes	100% Yes
10	Ultrasonic and sonic scalers are more ergonomical than hand scalers	54% yes 11% not sure	100% Yes
11	Light weight instruments help to reduce muscle fatigue.	77% Yes	100% Yes
12	Chair side exercises during clinical work can relieve pain due to improper posture.	67% Yes	100% Yes
13	Dentist Should take microbreaks(2-5mins) to reduce excessive muscle fatigue.	91% Yes	100% Yes
14	Tight or poor fitting gloves can cause pain in hands.	53% Yes 27% not sure	100% Yes
15	Ergonomics and musculoskeletal disorders should be included as a separate entity in the syllabus before students enter the clinic.	56% Yes 29% not sure	96% Yes